

PERCEPTIONS AND ATTITUDES OF COLLEGE TEACHERS TOWARDS
INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN GILGIT-BALTISTANMuhammad Hadi Haidari^{*1}, Saqib Husain², Asima³¹Ph.D. Scholar in Special Education, Lecturer, Department of Educational Development, Karakoram International University, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan²B.Ed. (Hons) Special Education, Department of Educational Development, Karakoram International University, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan³B.Ed. (Hons) Special Education, Department of Educational Development, Karakoram International University, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan¹mhadi578@yahoo.com, ²saqibsaq3832@gmail.com, ³asimaraza16@gmail.comDOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17656814>**Keywords**

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Abstract

This study examines the perceptions and attitudes of college teachers toward inclusive education in Gilgit-Baltistan, highlighting institutional support, existing barriers, and educators' readiness to implement inclusive practices. A quantitative survey design was employed using a structured Likert-scale questionnaire administered to 176 teachers (88 male and 88 female) from public and private colleges. Simple random sampling was used to ensure that every teacher had an equal chance of being selected. Findings revealed that most teachers hold positive attitudes toward inclusion, acknowledging its role in promoting equity, empathy, and academic success for all learners. However, implementation remains hindered by inadequate infrastructure, limited training, a lack of assistive technologies, and social stigma. Private college teachers demonstrated more favorable perceptions and institutional support than those in public colleges, while male teachers showed slightly higher awareness levels. The study underscores the need for continuous professional development, institutional reforms, and community sensitization to bridge the gap between inclusive education policies and classroom realities, fostering equitable learning environments across Gilgit-Baltistan.

INTRODUCTION

Inclusive education is an international process that guarantees all learners access to education equally with no discrimination based on intellectual, emotional, physical and social differences. It facilitates inclusion of students with special needs to standard classrooms and makes them feel part and develops them holistically (Nwile & Okwu, 2023). Inclusive education at the college level entails providing an environment in which students with disabilities can engage in both

academic and social activities with peers. It needs trained faculty, available infrastructure, and flexibility of the curriculum regulated by the Universal Design of learning to be effectively implemented (Hidayat, 2022). Inclusive education is observed to acknowledge the diversity of the needs of learners and the need to offer support to the learners accordingly. Through collaboration of teachers and institutions, the teachers and institutions are able to attain effective provision of cognitive, physical,

emotional, and cultural needs to the students to be able to participate meaningfully in both academic and social life. This process involves teacher preparation because the perceptions and attitudes of teachers play a central role in determining how inclusion is implemented within classrooms (Shadreck, 2012). Inclusion is a philosophy that advocates the rights of all students to experience general classroom curricula that are meaningful, challenging and have services and supports needed (Salend, 2011). The cooperation of general and special educators can improve the practices in the classroom and increase the learning outcomes (Rodriguez, 2021).

In Gilgit-Baltistan, the concept of inclusive education is taking root although it is being selectively applied because of infrastructural, professional and policy obstacles. Whereas training programs and sensitization have been improved, some institutions still do not have ramps, accessible wash rooms, assistive materials, and trained staff. Inclusion is further hampered by overcrowded classes, inflexible curricula and administration. These issues affect the perceptions of college teachers towards inclusive education, and it is crucial to investigate their attitudes, awareness, and readiness (Haideri and Parveen, 2025). This paper examines the perception and attitudes of college teachers in Gilgit-Baltistan against inclusive education. It explores how they interpret the principles of inclusivity, difficulties experienced in the implementation process, and how institutions support these efforts. The research results will be used to inform policy, teacher preparation and institution-wide approaches to promote equitable and inclusive education in the region as part of Pakistan's overall goal of ensuring that all learners have an equal chance to succeed in both academic and social settings in the inclusive classroom.

Statement of the Problem

Inclusive college classrooms present a number of barriers to the academic, social, and emotional growth of special needs students. Their mobility and participation is hampered by poor infrastructure (lack of ramps, lifts, and accessible toilets). The lack of trained specialists, such as special educators and counselors, also limits their academic interest and

emotional assistance. Most of the teachers are not trained and do not know about inclusive teaching practices which results in non-inclusive practices and materials. Stigma, isolation, and insufficient social acceptance of the students with disabilities can also be caused by negative views and attitudes of college teachers. This paper explores perceptions and attitudes of college teachers in Gilgit-Baltistan with regard to inclusive education with regards to the barriers, which includes lack of adequate infrastructure, training, resources, and social stigma. These challenges should be dealt with to guarantee fair representation of students with special needs in tertiary education. The research aims to bridge the current gap in knowledge about the attitude of teachers and the institutional facilitation needed to enhance effective inclusive education in the area (Gull and Basha, 2025).

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the support systems, training needs, and institutional strategies required to promote positive teacher attitudes and effective implementation of inclusive education at the college level in Gilgit-Baltistan.
2. To identify the key barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, lack of training, limited resources, and social stigma that influence teachers' perceptions and attitudes toward inclusive education.
3. To examine the perceptions of college teachers in Gilgit-Baltistan regarding inclusive education and their understanding of its purpose and significance.
4. To explore the attitudes of college teachers toward teaching students with special needs in inclusive classroom settings.
5. To explore how gender and type of institution affect college teachers' views and attitudes towards inclusive education in Gilgit-Baltistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Support Systems, Training Needs, and Institutional Strategies

Studies highlight that successful inclusive education is dependent on the inclusive teacher support

systems, appropriate training and institutional policies that maintain the practices of inclusiveness. Social and organization support is also a very important factor in the attitude of teachers towards inclusion and their confidence. Teachers show increased willingness and desire to embrace inclusive practice when they believe their administration supports them, colleagues collaborate, and resources are available to them (Desombre, Delaval, and Jury, 2021). One of the most important factors in the preparedness and acceptance of inclusion by teachers is training. Research has shown that more effective than one-day workshops is hands-on practical professional development centered on classroom management, differentiated instruction, and instruction with diverse learners. The long-term learning plans, including peer mentoring, joint planning, and communities of practice, assist educators to internalize the principles of inclusion and use them with confidence in actual classrooms (Daniela and Ecaterina, 2022). Higher education institutional support also is a key consideration towards the development of inclusive environments. Assistive technologies, accessible classes, counseling service, and positive institutional culture are some of the facilities that help to increase the participation of all learners. Those institutions which are more inclined to inclusivity with policies, leadership, and communication encourage higher teacher motivation and accountability (Filippou, Acquah, and Bengs, 2025). The perceptions of teachers are also crucial. Finland-based research also shows that the confidence of teachers, their common beliefs, and attitudes about managing classroom behavior have a highly significant influence on the outcomes of inclusion (Gülsun, Malinen, Yada, and Savolainen, 2023). In the same way, inclusive values that affirm diversity and equitable access are now taken seriously in universities across the globe, but there are still practical obstacles. Although the idea of inclusion is known, most higher education institutions cannot maintain marginalized students because of the lack of staff training, as well as because of inadequate application of policies that are inclusive (Ramachandran and Sujathamalini, 2024). Collectively, these results have shown that inclusive education is not just a matter of policy framework but also a matter of continuous teacher education,

institutional leadership and support systems that enable educators to effectively address the needs of the diverse learners..

Barriers to Inclusive Education

There are still barriers that make it hard to achieve inclusive education: inadequate infrastructure, lack of training, limited resources, and social stigma. The physical barrier such as no ramps, elevators, or adaptive learning rooms is still a significant issue in most institutions that limits access and movement of students with a disability. The teachers in these settings find it hard to make these adjustments to instruction, thus, making them less confident in inclusive teaching (Grant & Jones-Goods, 2016). The other significant obstacle is poor teacher training. Most teachers claim to get little training on special educational needs, adaptations in the class rooms, and differentiated instruction. Teachers are not ready and less motivated to embrace the inclusive approaches without the lifelong learning and development process (Odeh & Lach, 2024). Also, workshops that do not include practice opportunities do not develop confidence or competence.

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Implementation is also influenced by resource limits to a large degree. Absence of specialized personnel, aids, and resources forces teachers to operate under stress and make concessions on the inclusive practices (Awan et al., 2017). Indian studies also point at overcrowded classes, lack of funding as well as inadequate infrastructure as systemic barriers to encouraging teachers to embrace inclusive teaching. Progressive policies are limited in effectiveness due to the absence of monitoring and training (Shenoy, 2016).

Therefore, the existence of infrastructural, attitudinal, and resources based barriers still erodes inclusiveness in education. To get over these, it takes

both institutional reforms, specific teacher development and community involvement to alter perception and practice.

Perceptions of teachers towards inclusive education.

The perception of teachers plays a central role in the success of inclusive education because it directly affects the classroom practices and institutional culture. The idea of inclusive education is to eliminate any obstacles to learning and participation, yet its application is mostly based on the beliefs and willingness of educators.

Teachers in the higher education field mostly interpret inclusion in a way that is limited to supporting students with disabilities as opposed to a full-scale philosophy of fairness and diversity. There are no institutional definitions and training, which leads to discontinuity of knowledge. Although most teachers support the idea of inclusion in its original meaning, including physical access, they frequently confuse it with active involvement and engagement (Altes, Willemse, Goei, and Ehren, 2024). The perception of educators is formed by their experience and work with students with various needs. The direct experience of working with special needs students enables teachers to become more empathetic, aware, and confident (Mora, Chiva, and Lloret-Catala, 2021). Nevertheless, inclusion is still viewed by many as a policy requirement and not a pedagogical commitment (Rapp and Corral-Granados, 2024). The lack of proper dialogue, training, and institutional clarity makes the understanding incomplete and fragmented (Schmidt, Lešnjak, and Zurc, 2024).

According to recent research, the majority of educators are in favor of the concept of inclusion, but they are reluctant to modify the assessment, instructional approach, or curriculum because of workload, confusion, and institutional support. Significant transformation, however, is not just the matter of awareness, it is the case of institutional dedication, precise policies, and uninterrupted professional education (Ramdas et al., 2025).

College Teachers and their Attitudes towards Teaching Students with Special Needs.

Attitudes of teachers also play a major role in influencing the practice of inclusion in classrooms. The studies indicate that the rate of acceptance depends on the type of disability, with the teachers more ready to include students with a motor impairment than those with cognitive or developmental diseases (Jury, Perrin, Rohmer, and Desombre, 2021). There is also a difference in attitudes on training, experience and academic discipline. According to university research, the majority of teachers are in favor of the inclusion idea but complain of workload and resource burden and inability to understand implementation processes. The attitudes of female teachers and social sciences tend to be more favorable than those of natural sciences, which can be attributed to the impact of the academic culture and pre-training (Schmidt, Lešnjak, and Zurc, 2025). The primary concerns of the teachers are the lack of institutional support, insufficient training, and the uncertainty of inclusion. The typical worry associated with inclusion is that it would affect the quality of teaching or cause more issues in the classroom (Jury, Laurence, Cèbe, and Desombre, 2023). However, once teachers are properly trained, and the administration provides its support, their confidence and readiness to teach students with special needs rise significantly (Gal, Ryder, Amsalem, and d'OshratOn, 2025).

METHODOLOGY

The research design used in the study was quantitative research design involving a survey technique to understand the perception and attitude of college teachers towards inclusive education in Gilgit-Baltistan. The Likert-scale questionnaire was constructed using the applicable literature to collect academic, social, and institutional issues encountered in inclusive classes. The target population was comprised of about college teachers, out of which 176 teachers (88 males and 88 females) were selected by use of simple random sampling as a means to represent the various educational backgrounds. The questionnaire contained 40 closed-ended statements in four domains, namely, academic challenges, social challenges, accessibility of infrastructure, institutional support, and faculty and peer attitude. To achieve a content reliability, the

instrument was tested by a specialist in special education. The researcher personally collected the data by visiting several colleges where the responses were measured using SPSS 24 and descriptive statistics used to interpret the results including frequencies, percentages, and mean scores. The study was ethically conducted with the participants being

aware of the objective of the study, assured of confidentiality and free to withdraw at any time. The research was confined to the teachers in colleges in Gilgit-Baltistan and concentrated on issues and observations regarding inclusive education.

Results and analysis

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Special Education Teachers (N = 176)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	88	50.0
	Female	88	50.0
	Total	176	100.0
Age (Years)	20-29	101	57.4
	30-39	59	33.5
	40-49	13	7.4
	50 and above	3	1.7
	Total	176	100.0
Academic Qualification	MA/MSc	120	68.2
	MPhil	54	30.7
	PhD	2	1.1
	Total	176	100.0
Professional Qualification	B.Ed	63	35.8
	M.Ed	57	32.4
	Any Other	55	31.3
	Other (Unspecified)	1	0.6
	Total	176	100.0
Teaching Experience (Years)	Less than 5	86	48.9

	5-10	62	35.2
	11-15	24	13.6
	More than 15	4	2.3
	Total	176	100.0
Type of Institution	Public College	23	57.5
	Private College	17	42.5
	Total	40	100.0
Academic Discipline	Arts	75	42.6
	Science	65	36.9
	IT	36	20.5
	Total	176	100.0
Inclusive Training	Yes	35	19.89%
	No	141	80.11%
	Total	176	100.0
Teaching Experience with PWDs	Yes	76	43.2
	No	100	56.8
	Total	176	100.0

Table 1 presents the demographic and professional characteristics of the study participants. The gender distribution is equally split, with 50% male and 50% female. Most participants (57.4%) are aged 20-29, followed by 33.5% in the 30-39 range. In terms of academic qualifications, 68.2% hold an MA/MSc, while 30.7% have an MPhil. For professional qualifications, B.Ed (35.8%) and M.Ed (32.4%) are the most common. Regarding teaching experience, \

48.9% have less than 5 years, and 35.2% have 5-10 years. Most participants work in public colleges (57.5%), and a majority teach in the arts (42.6%). A significant portion (80.1%) has not received inclusive education training, and 43.2% have experience teaching students with disabilities. This demographic overview provides a clear context for understanding the participants' perspectives on inclusive education.

Table.2 Descriptive Statistics of Respondents' Perceptions of Institutional Support for Inclusive Education

Statements	SD	DA	NU	A	SA	Mean	Std. Deviation
My college provides adequate administrative support for implementing inclusive education.	15 (8.5%)	19 (10.8%)	32 (18.2%)	71 (40.3%)	39 (22.2%)	3.57	1.10
There are sufficient institutional policies that promote inclusive teaching practices.	8 (4.5%)	27 (15.3%)	38 (21.6%)	71 (40.3%)	32 (18.2%)	3.52	1.23
I have access to professional development opportunities focused on inclusive education.	11 (6.3%)	21 (11.9%)	37 (21.0%)	70 (39.8%)	37 (21.0%)	3.57	1.28
My institution provides access to special educators or resource persons for guidance.	19 (10.8%)	19 (10.8%)	49 (27.8%)	61 (34.7%)	28 (15.9%)	3.34	1.39
The college administration encourages collaboration among teachers to promote inclusion.	14 (8.0%)	24 (13.6%)	29 (16.5%)	59 (33.5%)	50 (28.4%)	3.61	1.11
My institution provides adequate teaching aids and learning materials for inclusive classrooms.	15 (8.5%)	23 (13.1%)	37 (21.0%)	59 (33.5%)	42 (23.9%)	3.51	1.14
The curriculum used in my college supports the inclusion of students with diverse learning needs.	18 (10.2%)	19 (10.8%)	36 (20.5%)	71 (40.3%)	32 (18.2%)	3.45	1.15
There is a clear strategy or plan in my college for the implementation of inclusive education.	18 (10.2%)	24 (13.6%)	42 (23.9%)	67 (38.1%)	25 (14.2%)	3.32	1.20
I receive encouragement and appreciation from my institution for practicing inclusive teaching methods.	10 (5.7%)	19 (10.8%)	39 (22.2%)	77 (43.8%)	31 (17.6%)	3.57	1.17
The existing support systems in my college positively influence my attitude toward inclusive education.	14 (8.0%)	23 (13.1%)	49 (27.8%)	46 (26.1%)	44 (25.0%)	3.47	1.18

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of respondents' perceptions of institutional support for inclusive education. The responses indicate varied perceptions across different statements. For instance, the majority of respondents (62.5%) agreed or strongly agreed that their college provides adequate administrative support for implementing inclusive education (mean = 3.57), while 34.6% disagreed or strongly disagreed about having access to special educators or resource persons (mean = 3.34). Professional development opportunities and teaching aids received similar positive responses, with means

of 3.57 and 3.51, respectively. The perception of institutional policies promoting inclusive practices was slightly lower, with a mean of 3.52. The responses also highlighted that while collaboration among teachers to promote inclusion is encouraged, the clarity of strategies or plans for implementing inclusive education received a somewhat less favorable view (mean = 3.32). Overall, respondents expressed moderate to positive perceptions of institutional support, with standard deviations indicating varied responses across participants.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Respondents' Perceptions of Barriers to Inclusive Education

Statements	SD	DA	NU	A	SA	Mean	Std. Deviation
My college lacks the necessary infrastructure (e.g., ramps, accessible classrooms).	17 (9.7%)	34 (19.3%)	29 (16.5%)	72 (40.9%)	24 (13.6%)	3.30	1.20
There are insufficient financial resources allocated for inclusive education programs.	16 (9.1%)	29 (16.5%)	35 (19.9%)	52 (29.5%)	44 (25.0%)	3.45	1.25
Large class sizes make it difficult to provide individualized attention.	17 (9.7%)	34 (19.3%)	24 (13.6%)	65 (36.9%)	36 (20.5%)	3.39	1.22
Lack of professional development opportunities affects my confidence in teaching inclusively.	19 (10.8%)	31 (17.6%)	34 (19.3%)	56 (31.8%)	36 (20.5%)	3.34	1.28
Limited access to assistive technologies hinders participation of students with disabilities.	20 (11.4%)	19 (10.8%)	43 (24.4%)	57 (32.4%)	37 (21.0%)	3.41	1.21
Insufficient administrative support for implementing inclusive practices in my college.	23 (13.1%)	28 (15.9%)	42 (23.9%)	55 (31.3%)	28 (15.9%)	3.21	1.30
Negative societal attitudes toward disability create challenges for inclusive education.	12 (6.8%)	20 (11.4%)	41 (23.3%)	64 (36.4%)	39 (22.2%)	3.56	1.18
Some colleagues show resistance or indifference toward inclusive education initiatives.	22 (12.5%)	30 (17.0%)	38 (21.6%)	54 (30.7%)	32 (18.2%)	3.25	1.27
Students without disabilities sometimes show reluctance to interact with peers who have special needs.	21 (11.9%)	18 (10.2%)	38 (21.6%)	66 (37.5%)	33 (18.8%)	3.41	1.23
Cultural and social stigma in the community negatively affects teachers' motivation to adopt inclusive practices.	15 (8.5%)	31 (17.6%)	41 (23.3%)	51 (29.0%)	38 (21.6%)	3.38	1.24

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics of respondents' perceptions of barriers to inclusive education. The findings reveal various challenges faced by participants. The most commonly reported barrier is insufficient financial resources for inclusive education programs (mean = 3.45), followed by large class sizes hindering individualized attention (mean = 3.39). Respondents also highlighted a lack of infrastructure (mean = 3.30) and limited access to assistive technologies (mean = 3.41) as significant

barriers. The perception of insufficient administrative support for inclusive practices had a lower mean (3.21), while societal attitudes and cultural stigma were also recognized as barriers, with mean scores of 3.56 and 3.38, respectively. Overall, the standard deviations indicate some variability in responses, suggesting that the impact of these barriers is perceived differently by different respondents.

Table.4 Descriptive Statistics of Respondents' Perceptions of Teachers' Perceptions of Inclusive Education

Statements	SD	DA	NU	A	SA	Mean	Std. Deviation
I have a clear understanding of what inclusive education means.	17 (9.7%)	20 (11.4%)	29 (16.5%)	66 (37.5%)	44 (25.0%)	3.57	1.12
Inclusive education aims to ensure equal learning opportunities for all students, including those with special needs.	12 (6.8%)	18 (10.2%)	35 (19.9%)	54 (30.7%)	57 (32.4%)	3.72	1.15
I believe inclusive education promotes social acceptance among students.	18 (10.2%)	25 (14.2%)	32 (18.2%)	58 (33.0%)	42 (23.9%)	3.46	1.18
Inclusive education helps develop empathy and cooperation among all learners.	11 (6.3%)	20 (11.4%)	26 (14.8%)	74 (42.0%)	45 (25.6%)	3.69	1.10
Teachers play a vital role in promoting the purpose and values of inclusive education.	16 (9.1%)	21 (11.9%)	30 (17.0%)	63 (35.8%)	46 (26.1%)	3.58	1.13
Inclusive education is essential for achieving educational equity in Gilgit-Baltistan.	14 (8.0%)	19 (10.8%)	34 (19.3%)	63 (35.8%)	46 (26.1%)	3.61	1.14
I believe inclusive classrooms benefit both students with and without disabilities.	18 (10.2%)	15 (8.5%)	33 (18.8%)	74 (42.0%)	36 (20.5%)	3.54	1.16
Inclusive education contributes positively to the academic achievement of students with special needs.	16 (9.1%)	10 (5.7%)	35 (19.9%)	61 (34.7%)	54 (30.7%)	3.72	1.12
I perceive inclusive education as an effective approach to reducing discrimination in schools and colleges.	19 (10.8%)	22 (12.5%)	27 (15.3%)	70 (39.8%)	38 (21.6%)	3.49	1.18
I believe teachers' positive perceptions can greatly influence the success of inclusive education.	12 (6.8%)	16 (9.1%)	22 (12.5%)	75 (42.6%)	51 (29.0%)	3.78	1.10

Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics of respondents' perceptions of teachers' views on inclusive education. The majority of respondents expressed a strong understanding of inclusive education, with the statement "I have a clear understanding of what inclusive education means" receiving a mean score of 3.57. Teachers generally agreed that inclusive education promotes equal learning opportunities (mean = 3.72) and helps develop empathy and cooperation among students (mean = 3.69). They also perceived inclusive education as beneficial for both students with and

without disabilities (mean = 3.54). The statement "I believe teachers' positive perceptions can greatly influence the success of inclusive education" received the highest mean score of 3.78, indicating a strong belief in the role of teachers in fostering inclusive education. However, some variability is evident in the responses, as shown by the standard deviations, suggesting diverse opinions on the effectiveness of inclusive education in reducing discrimination and promoting social acceptance. Overall, the data highlights generally positive perceptions among teachers toward inclusive education.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of Teachers' Attitudes toward Inclusive Education (TAIE) (N = 176)

Statements	SD	DA	NU	A	SA	Mean	Std. Deviation
I feel comfortable teaching students with special needs in my regular classroom.	11 (6.3%)	21 (11.9%)	44 (25.0%)	57 (32.4%)	43 (24.4%)	3.57	1.12
I believe students with special needs can learn effectively alongside their peers in inclusive settings.	17 (9.7%)	27 (15.3%)	23 (13.1%)	77 (43.8%)	32 (18.2%)	3.45	1.15
I am willing to modify lesson plans to meet the needs of students with disabilities.	15 (8.5%)	20 (11.4%)	44 (25.0%)	61 (34.7%)	36 (20.5%)	3.47	1.14
Teaching students with special needs adds valuable diversity to the classroom experience.	15 (8.5%)	24 (13.6%)	35 (19.9%)	67 (38.1%)	35 (19.9%)	3.47	1.13
I feel motivated to use inclusive teaching strategies in my classroom.	15 (8.5%)	19 (10.8%)	28 (15.9%)	68 (38.6%)	46 (26.1%)	3.63	1.11
I believe that students with special needs have the potential to perform well academically in regular classrooms.	15 (8.5%)	13 (7.4%)	40 (22.7%)	57 (32.4%)	51 (29.0%)	3.66	1.12
I find inclusive education to be a positive and rewarding experience for teachers.	12 (6.8%)	23 (13.1%)	40 (22.7%)	56 (31.8%)	45 (25.6%)	3.56	1.13
I am willing to attend additional training or workshops on inclusive education.	16 (9.1%)	17 (9.7%)	33 (18.8%)	60 (34.1%)	50 (28.4%)	3.63	1.11
I believe inclusive classrooms promote equality and respect among students.	12 (6.8%)	20 (11.4%)	33 (18.8%)	68 (38.6%)	43 (24.4%)	3.63	1.10
I feel that teaching students with disabilities does not negatively affect the learning of other students.	20 (11.4%)	18 (10.2%)	25 (14.2%)	57 (32.4%)	56 (31.8%)	3.63	1.14

Table 5 show that the teachers mostly show positive attitudes towards inclusive education. The most frequent mean scores were noted on such statements as: I believe that students with special needs can also

achieve well in regular classrooms (M = 3.66) and I feel motivated to apply inclusive teaching strategies in my classroom (M = 3.63) indicating that the majority of the teachers believe in the abilities of

students with disabilities and themselves have the motivation to use inclusive teaching methods. In the same manner, the willingness to engage in additional training among respondents was quite high ($M = 3.63$), and inclusion was perceived as a driver of equality and respect between students ($M = 3.63$). There was a moderate agreement on such items as the one that teaches students with special needs is a comfortable and fulfilling experience ($M = 3.57$) and the one that says inclusive education is a positive and rewarding experience ($M = 3.56$), which suggests that though teachers are not negative towards working

with them, they still need support and confidence-building. The fact that the mean values of statements about lesson modification ($M = 3.47$) and classroom diversity ($M = 3.47$) are relatively lower is the indication of some practical difficulties in changing the teaching approach to match the needs of inclusive environments. Altogether, the results indicate that educators in Gilgit-Baltistan have positive and optimistic attitudes to inclusive education but can be supported with specific professional development to increase their teaching confidence and inclusive teaching skills.

Table 6. Independent Samples t-test Results for Gender Differences in Perceptions of Inclusive Education (N = 176)

Variable	Gender	Mean	tvalue	df	pvalue	95% Confidence Interval
College Support for Inclusive Education	Male	3.62	0.80	174	.423	-0.12, 0.28
	Female	3.54				
Barriers to Inclusive Teaching	Male	3.66	2.48	174	.014	0.05, 0.45
	Female	3.40				
Teachers' Perceptions and Understanding of Inclusive Education	Male	3.83	2.66	174	.009	0.07, 0.49
	Female	3.55				
Teachers' Attitudes toward Inclusive Classroom Settings	Male	3.74	2.43	174	.016	0.05, 0.44
	Female	3.49				

The Results of the Independent Samples t-test in Table 6 demonstrate the differences in the perception of male and female respondents about inclusive education. The results demonstrate that there are some gender distinctions in various areas. In the case of College Support for Inclusive Education, males ($M = 3.62$) and females ($M = 3.54$) had similar perceptions with no significant distinction ($t = 0.80, p = .423$). There were however considerable differences in other variables. Males showed higher means in Barriers to Inclusive

Teaching ($M = 3.66$ vs. 3.40), Teachers Perceptions and Understanding of Inclusive Education ($M = 3.83$ vs. 3.55) and attitudes towards including ($M = 3.74$ vs. 3.49), and these results can be regarded as an indication of higher understanding of inclusive education by male teachers as opposed to women. All in all, it is possible to note that even though both genders have positive perceptions of inclusive education, male teachers demonstrated a better knowledge.

Table 7. Independent Samples t-test Results for Institutional Differences in Perceptions of Inclusive Education (N = 176)

Variable	Type of Institution	Mean	t value	df	p value	95% Confidence Interval
College Support for Inclusive Education	Public College	3.18	-7.63	174	.000	-0.85, -0.50
	Private College	3.86				
Barriers to Inclusive Teaching	Public College	3.15	-6.93	174	.000	-0.83, -0.46
	Private College	3.79				
Teachers' Perceptions and Understanding of Inclusive Education	Public College	3.33	-6.10	174	.000	-0.81, -0.41
	Private College	3.94				
Teachers' Attitudes toward Inclusive Classroom Settings	Public College	3.30	-5.65	174	.000	-0.73, -0.35
	Private College	3.83				

Table 7 shows the Independent Samples t-test outcomes of the perceptions of inclusive education between the respondents of the public and the private colleges. As a result of the analysis, the support in College Support for Inclusive Education, respondents of the private colleges (M = 3.86) scored higher in support than the respondents of the public colleges (M = 3.18), and the difference in the score was extremely significant ($t = -7.63$, $p = .000$). In the same way, the Barriers to Inclusive Teaching were seen to be higher in private colleges (M = 3.79) than in public ones (M = 3.15), $t = -6.93$, $p = .000$. Strong Perceptions and Understanding of Inclusive Education (M = 3.94) were also observed in respondents of the private institutions (as compared to public institutions) creating a significant difference ($t = -6.10$, $p = .000$). Similarly, Teachers Attitudes toward Inclusive Classroom Settings were more positive in private colleges (M = 3.83) than in the public one (M = 3.30), $t = -5.65$, $p = .000$, the result indicates that the institutional commitment and awareness in the former environments where they were more positive.

Summary

The paper will examine the perceptions and understanding of inclusive education by college teachers in Gilgit-Baltistan and emphasize the

advances and challenges that still exist in the educational institutions of the region. The education movement of inclusiveness, which promotes the equality of learning opportunities to all students irrespective of their abilities and backgrounds, is not yet developed in Gilgit-Baltistan because of the lack of infrastructural and institutional capacity. The study was conducted to determine the perceptions of the teachers, barriers, and assess the institutional support mechanisms that determine inclusive practices. The survey design adopted was that of quantitative surveys where a sample of 176 college teachers (88 men and 88 women) was selected by use of simple random sampling. The questionnaire has 40 items which include four dimensions which are institutional support, barriers to inclusion, the perceptions of teachers, and attitudes of teachers. The SPSS data analysis showed that teachers in general, have positive perceptions and attitudes towards inclusion, but a number of barriers at the system level limit implementation. The results indicated that the institutional support was moderate, particularly in encouraging teachers to collaborate and offer them a chance to develop professionally. Nevertheless, such aspects as the availability of special educators, assistive technologies, and institutional plans to support inclusion are still weak. Educationalists realized the

importance of inclusion in ensuring equity, empathy and academic success among the learners with special needs. They also said they were willing to changes in lessons, take additional training and employ inclusive methods, but due to practical limitations like large classroom sizes, lack of resources and administrative support undermined their confidence. The findings also showed a difference between men and women and between big and small institutions: male teachers were a bit more aware and positive in their attitudes, whereas teachers of a private college were more supportive of and understanding of inclusion in their policies than their colleagues in public colleges.

Discussion

The results of this research bring significant information to the existing picture of the current inclusivity in the field of education in Gilgit-Baltistan, especially the perception, attitude, and institutional preparedness of college teachers. In general, the findings are that the teachers in the area have positive attitudes towards inclusive education and understand the significance of inclusive education in enhancing equity, empathy and social acceptance among the students. However, the research also indicates that there are major structural, attitudinal, and institutional barriers that are still in the way of complete adoption of inclusive practices. The conceptual knowledge among teachers regarding inclusive education and its objectives was good, and this proved the previous studies that relate teacher awareness to more positive views towards inclusion (Arranz-Sánchez and Espada-Chavarria, 2025). The majority of the respondents were in agreement that inclusion is helpful to both students with and without disabilities, as it contributes to developing cooperation and empathy in the classrooms. This indicates that the issue of inclusion is increasingly becoming relevant to teachers in Gilgit-Baltistan due to insight into the importance of this philosophy as every learner has the right to access mainstream education. Nevertheless, that positive attitude was accompanied by a great deal of confusion about how to implement it because of not having resources, training, and institutional support, which is also consistent with the findings of Odeh and Lach (2024) and Grant and Jones-Goods (2016)

who also found that poor preparation and infrastructure undermines the confidence that teachers have towards inclusive settings.

Institutional backing proved to be a major factor in the positive attitudinal determination. Teachers cited administrative support, professional development prospects, and collaborative efforts with their colleagues as factors that improve their motivation to use inclusive practices. However, the lack of special educators, assistive resources, and clear institutional plans indicate that the inclusiveness in higher education is more of a policy issue than a practice one. These blank spaces show that, although institutions are recognizing the concept of inclusion, there are still no tangible frameworks and regularized monitoring systems. On the same note, other developing regions have also reported similar problems where leadership and institutional preparedness are key in perpetuating inclusive reforms (Filippou, Acquah, and Bengs, 2025).

Among the most commonly mentioned barriers were lack of proper infrastructure, negative perceptions in the society, and lack of financial means. Educators identified that the issue of cultural stigma and community awareness has a significant impact on inclusive education of students with disabilities, which is consistent with previous research by Coelho, Blázquez, and Cubo (2017) pointing to the role of social attitudes on the inclusivity in education. The fact that these barriers have been persistent in Gilgit-Baltistan is a requirement to take a holistic approach to the issue that incorporates community level sensitization strategies alongside institutional and policy level interventions. Unless these sociocultural aspects are considered, even institutional policies which are well-intended, might fail to deliver any significant results. The gender and institutional comparisons in the study provide additional information. The difference between male and female teachers is that male teachers indicated little more than female teachers were aware and confident of implementing inclusive education, and this may be because of differences in exposure or access to training. More to the point, even the professors at the private colleges had a higher degree of institutional support and more positive attitudes towards inclusion than those in public colleges. This implies that there are possibilities that the private

colleges within Gilgit-Baltistan have looser policies, a more developed infrastructure or more proactive leadership when it comes to advancing inclusivity. The public institutions, however, are seen to be limited by the bureaucratic organization and the absence of funds that make it difficult to be innovative in its teaching and adopting the curriculum. All these findings point to the interdependence of teacher attitudes and institutional support, and more extensive systemic conditions. Inclusive education is not a one-sided training or infrastructural changes and, instead, a concerted approach by policymakers, administrators, educators, and communities. To bridge the gap between policy intentions and classroom realities, teacher training programs should be strengthened, resource allocation improved and an institutional culture of encouragement developed. Further, ongoing professional learning that involves practical, hands-on experiences would enable the teachers to be highly confident in managing diversity in their lessons, although, the study confirms that teachers in Gilgit-Baltistan are largely supportive of inclusive education, real changes would be achieved through sustained institutional commitment and greater policy implementation and cultural change. With the enhancement of structural and attitudinal barriers, educational institutions should be able to develop more inclusive, equitable, and safe environments where every learner despite their ability can succeed in their studies and social life.

Findings

1. Positive Attitudes to Inclusion:

The majority of the teachers showed a good grasp of the concept of inclusive education and its objectives. They accepted that inclusive education is the access to equal learning, social acceptance, and empathy among students. Teachers admitted that inclusion can help not only disabled students, but also students without disabilities, and it can positively influence the academic performance of every learner.

2. Moderate Institutional Support:

The respondents largely thought their institutions were moderately accommodating inclusivity. Teachers mentioned that the most remarkable strengths included administrative support, collaboration, and cooperation between colleagues.

In a few colleges there were professional development opportunities but training was minimal and infrequent. Access to special educators, assistive materials as well as institutionalized strategies of inclusion, however, were still insufficient.

3. Barriers to Implementation:

The research found various obstacles preventing successful inclusion in colleges. The greatest barriers were found to be poor attitudes of society towards disability, lack of financial support, unavailability of assistive technology and high classroom sizes. Assessment of the lack of clear institutional structures, administrative support, and opposition of some colleagues were also mentioned by teachers as some reasons that limit inclusive education practices.

4. Attitudes of Teachers to Inclusive Education:

Comprehensively, educators were positive and optimistic towards teaching students with special needs. They reported being motivated to use inclusive teaching methods, ready to change lesson plans, and eager to take part in additional training. It was widely believed that inclusion fosters equality and respect among the students. But their reluctance to acknowledge their capabilities in handling diverse classrooms remained in some teachers and it signifies that more practical training and institutional support is required.

5. Gender Differences:

Gender analysis revealed that male teachers had a little higher average score than female teachers in perceptions, understanding, and attitudes towards inclusive education. Males also found more obstacles to inclusion, which could be a reflection of a greater sensitivity to the problem of institutional systems.

6. Institutional Differences:

The mean scores of teachers in the four dimensions, namely college support, barriers, perceptions, and attitudes, among the teachers in the private colleges were significantly higher than those of the teachers in the public colleges. This indicates that private institutions in Gilgit-Baltistan offer more administrative support, awareness, and more conducive conditions to inclusive education, and the public institutions are subjected to infrastructural and administrative limitations.

7. Professional Development and Policy Reform Requirement:

The results highlight that inclusion is conceptually supported by teachers, but it is not implemented in practice because there is no long-term training and direction of the policy. The three areas of constant professional development, institutional planning, and better funding mechanisms are highly desirable in order to enhance inclusive education in the area.

Recommendations

- 1. Enhance Professional Development Programs:** Continuous, practical, and experience-based training workshops should be conducted to strengthen teachers' skills and confidence in handling inclusive classrooms. These programs should focus on differentiated instruction, assistive technology integration, and classroom management for diverse learners.
- 2. Strengthen Institutional Support Systems:** Colleges should establish inclusion-focused committees to coordinate support services, ensure accessibility, and provide resource persons such as special educators and counselors. Institutional policies must clearly outline implementation strategies for inclusive practices.
- 3. Improve Infrastructure and Accessibility:** Educational institutions should invest in physical infrastructure such as ramps, elevators, and accessible washrooms to create barrier-free environments for students with disabilities. Digital and assistive learning tools must also be made readily available.
- 4. Promote Community Awareness and Collaboration:** Awareness campaigns and parent-teacher-community partnerships are essential to overcome social stigma and cultural barriers that hinder inclusion. Collaborative efforts can foster empathy and support for students with special needs.
- 5. Policy Reforms and Government Intervention:** Provincial education authorities should allocate targeted funding for inclusive education programs, ensuring equitable resource distribution between public and private institutions. Policy frameworks should be revised

to include monitoring mechanisms that evaluate implementation effectiveness.

6. Encourage Research and Data-Driven Strategies:

Further research on inclusion in higher education should be encouraged to monitor progress, identify gaps, and propose context-specific solutions for improving inclusivity across Gilgit-Baltistan.

REFERENCES

- Altes, F., Willemse, M., Goei, S. L., & Ehren, M. (2024). *Teachers' perceptions of inclusion and its impact on instructional practices*. *Journal of Inclusive Education Research*, 18(2), 134-150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/jiers.2024.011>
- Arranz-Sánchez, R., & Espada-Chavarría, R. (2025). *Teachers' awareness and attitudes toward inclusion: A cross-regional analysis*. *International Journal of Inclusive Pedagogy*, 9(1), 25-44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/ijip.2025.09.002>
- Awan, A., Aslam, M., & Zafar, S. (2017). *Barriers to inclusive education in developing countries: A Pakistani perspective*. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 45(3), 101-112.
- Coelho, V., Blázquez, D., & Cubo, S. (2017). *Social attitudes and inclusion of students with disabilities in higher education*. *International Education Studies*, 10(4), 56-69.
- Daniela, S., & Ecaterina, B. (2022). *Professional development and inclusive practices among higher education faculty*. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 8(11), 45-63.
- Desombre, C., Delaval, M., & Jury, M. (2021). *Teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy toward inclusive education: The role of institutional support*. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 99, 103279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103279>
- Filippou, K., Acquah, E. O., & Bengs, A. (2025). *Institutional culture and inclusive education: Insights from higher education contexts*. *International Review of Education*, 71(1), 45-62.
- Gal, E., Ryder, E., Amsalem, M., & d'OshratOn, S. (2025). *Teacher readiness and motivation for inclusion in secondary classrooms*. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 117(3), 205-221.

- Grant, K., & Jones-Goods, E. (2016). *Infrastructure challenges to inclusive education: A comparative study*. *Journal of Educational Development*, 56(2), 89–103.
- Gülsun, M., Malinen, O., Yada, A., & Savolainen, H. (2023). *Teacher confidence and inclusive education outcomes: Evidence from Finland*. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 38(4), 550–568.
- Gull, S., & Basha, N. (2025). *Institutional barriers and teacher attitudes toward inclusive education in northern Pakistan*. *Pakistan Journal of Educational Studies*, 33(1), 85–104.
- Haideri, A., & Parveen, F. (2025). *Implementation challenges of inclusive education in Gilgit-Baltistan*. *Asian Journal of Education and Development*, 12(1), 74–89.
- Hidayat, R. (2022). *Curriculum flexibility and inclusive higher education: A Universal Design for Learning perspective*. *International Journal of Education and Learning*, 6(4), 221–239.
- Jury, M., Laurence, L., Cèbe, S., & Desombre, C. (2023). *Teachers' perceptions of classroom inclusion and student diversity*. *European Educational Research Journal*, 22(5), 742–758.
- Jury, M., Perrin, M., Rohmer, O., & Desombre, C. (2021). *Teachers' acceptance of students with disabilities: Differences by type of impairment*. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 68(3), 289–308.
- Lindsay, G. (2007). *Educational psychology and the effectiveness of inclusive education programs*. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 77(1), 1–24.
- Mora, T., Chiva, I., & Lloret-Català, M. (2021). *Teacher experiences and perceptions toward inclusive higher education*. *Journal of Education and Social Inclusion*, 4(2), 112–130.
- Nwile, C., & Okwu, P. (2023). *Inclusive education and social justice in higher learning institutions*. *International Journal of Educational Inclusion*, 5(2), 98–115.
- Odeh, L., & Lach, H. (2024). *Teacher training and readiness for inclusive education in resource-limited settings*. *Education and Development Review*, 39(2), 211–229.
- Ramachandran, P., & Sujathamalini, S. (2024). *Policy frameworks for inclusive education in South Asia: Progress and gaps*. *Comparative Education Review*, 68(2), 189–204.
- Ramdas, K., Pillai, M., & Ananth, R. (2025). *Transforming teacher beliefs through inclusive pedagogy training*. *Asian Journal of Teacher Education*, 14(3), 201–218.
- Rapp, C., & Corral-Granados, D. (2024). *Inclusive education as a pedagogical commitment: Teachers' perspectives in higher education*. *Higher Education Research Journal*, 20(1), 45–62.
- Rodriguez, D. (2021). *Collaboration between general and special educators: Impact on inclusive practices*. *Journal of Special Education Leadership*, 34(3), 211–223.
- Salend, S. J. (2011). *Creating inclusive classrooms: Effective and reflective practices* (7th ed.). Pearson.
- Schmidt, M., Lešnjak, L., & Zurc, J. (2024). *Understanding inclusion: Teacher perceptions and institutional realities*. *Journal of Educational Inclusion Studies*, 19(2), 147–168.
- Schmidt, M., Lešnjak, L., & Zurc, J. (2025). *Disciplinary differences in teacher attitudes toward inclusion in higher education*. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning*, 29(1), 67–82.
- Shadreck, M. (2012). *Teacher preparedness for inclusive education: A Zimbabwean case study*. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 7(1), 50–63.
- Shenoy, S. (2016). *Systemic barriers to inclusive education: Lessons from India*. *Education and Society*, 34(2), 78–94.